

Optimal Motivation among Adolescents in Relation to Parental Involvement

Dr. Jasmeet Kaur Bedi

Asstt. Prof. BCM College of Education, Ludhiana

ABSTRACT

Background: Optimal motivation is the main thrust which settles on a person to settle on productive decisions, control his learning exercises and feels satisfaction and joy in doing each assignment or action. Yet, we can't overlook this reality that a few understudies are basically not inspired without help from anyone else. It is the educators, guardians who make them roused. It is of incredible worry for instructors to create and keep up with understudies' optimal motivated. Especially during pre-adulthood stage, numerous understudies experience an absence of motivation to take part in scholastic exercises and neglect to arrive at their scholarly potential. Thusly, the motivation of students has been the focal point of much examination. Motivation is presumably the main factor that teachers can focus to further develop learning. The truth of the matter is that individuals overall and understudies specifically are perplexing animals with complex requirements and wants. With respect to understudies, very little if any learning can happen except if understudies are spurred consistently. Motivation has been and keeps on being a broadly concentrated on region across a considerable lot of life's areas. Motivation is the stimulating power that starts and supports conduct and eventually creates results. The principle objective of the review was to look at optimal motivation among adolescents in relation to parental involvement. To achieve the evenhanded, Optimal Motivation Scale constructed and developed by the investigator and Parental Involvement Scale by Dr. Sangeeta Tramma, 1998 were embraced.

Materials and methods: The descriptive survey method was employed for the present investigation. The sample comprises of 464 adolescents studied in CBSE affiliated schools of Ludhiana district of Punjab. Data has been drawn from students of 9th and 10th class. The sample was further drawn from male and female students. Sample has been selected by employing simple random sampling technique, Stratified random sampling technique, purposive sampling technique and systematic random sampling technique.

Results: Findings of the study reveal significant relationship between optimal motivation of adolescents with personal involvement and cognitive stimulation dimensions of parental involvement; significant relationship between optimal motivation of male adolescents with cognitive stimulation dimension of parental involvement and significant relationship between optimal motivation of female adolescents with personal involvement, behavior involvement and cognitive stimulation dimensions of parental involvement.

Conclusion: The current review would have useful ramifications for directing the parents to be more associated with the academics and professional existences of their children so their wards can feel more roused, allowed to do any course, use sound judgment in regards to their schooling and vocation. The review will urge the guardians to propel their girl child so they can turn out to be surer and skilled that is the need of hour. The review would have down to earth suggestions for the educators, instructive organizers and strategy creators to arrange such kinds of projects that help the parents and understudies to know the significance of optimal motivation.

KEYWORD: Optimal Motivation, Parental Involvement, Adolescents.

I. INTRODUCTION

Optimal Motivation

Optimal motivation is something that can be instructed, learned, supported, and maintained. People or understudies can be helped how to pick an excellent optimal involvement with any time and for any assignment. Optimal motivation is an original idea in the field of motivation, assisting a person with understanding that individuals are constantly spurred and it relies on the nature of their motivation that matters most.

Optimal motivation is to learn self-guideline and care to accomplish and support elite and positive prosperity. Optimal motivation is a condition or state where an individual encounters the advantages of fulfilling their three mental requirements for example

Optimal Motivation among Adolescents in Relation to Parental Involvement

independence, relatedness, and capability in the pursuit and accomplishment of significant objectives that prompts positive and manageable energy, essentialness, and feeling of prosperity. This must be accomplished through top notch self-guideline: When individuals can accomplish their objective with created values, interface themselves to a respectable reason, or feel the delight and satisfaction from doing that task paying little heed to any outer rewards or inciting. Optimal motivation is like having a positive energy, essentialness, and feeling of prosperity. Optimal motivation is an ability that includes having the option to distinguish your present persuasive viewpoint or shift to or keeps an optimal motivation a standpoint through self-guideline techniques, and to think about sentiments when individuals experience optimal motivation they need to an ever increasing extent.

In view of the study of Self-Assurance Hypothesis; Standards of optimal motivation are:

1. People have a natural tendency for development, advancement, and coordinated working, however this tendency regularly gets undermine by outside powers.
2. There are likewise some particular natural and individual factors that either favor or against this intrinsic demeanor to blast or grow.
3. The most basic component is the fulfillment of requirements for Independence, Relatedness, and Ability, or Circular segment.

Parental Involvement

Parental involvement is continually felt a subject of studies and discourse in adolescents' motivation. Parental involvement is characterized on the grounds that the educator's idea of the great quality mentality of mother and father towards their children schooling, teacher, and school (Webster-Stratton, 1998) Parental involvement in tutoring as parental conduct with, or in the interest of children, at homegrown or at school, notwithstanding the anticipations that father and mother hold for youth's future instruction (Berthelsen and Walker, 2008).

Hoover, Kathleen and Sandler composed article on parent involvement in youngsters' preparation: For what reason does it have an effect? Which transformed into posted in 1995 characterized parental contribution comprehensively to envelop homegrown based thoroughly sports (e.g., supporting with schoolwork, examining school events or guides) and staff based exercises (e.g., chipping in at personnel, coming to secondary school exercises). They thought that parental involvement is a created from a decide convictions around their jobs and commitments, a figure's experience that they can help her children arrive at school, and the opportunities for inclusion provided by utilizing the everyday schedule. They comparatively investigated while guardians get stressed; youngster's preparation or achievement is influenced through their securing of data, abilities, and through certainty. Peters (2012) said that on the point while universities have gotten reputation for being productive, they for the most part have heaps of commitment from parents. (Nihat, Sad and Gurbuzturk 2013) referenced that achievement at personnel is guaranteed if school essentially based directing is supported with the guide of parent's involvement at home. Contribution of parents in schooling has been expressed to yield fine results in various respects comprising of student interest, higher academic achievement, thought, workforce association, obligation and assurance, better friendly change and considerably less request inconveniences.

By dissecting the investigations on optimal motivation and parental involvement, the researcher has arrived at the conclusion that the majority of the examinations were associated with the variable intrinsic motivation, role of motivation, extraneous motivation, academic motivation, achievement motivation and impact of motivation. The researcher explored just review led by Rea, 2000 under the title optimal motivation for talent development and the results of study upheld that optimal motivation is essential for talent development. Studies led by Gottfried, Fleming and Gottfried, 1994; Alyssa, Willems and Holbein, 2005; Gonida, 2007; Hoang, 2007; Rivers, 2008; Grolnick, Friendly and Bellas, 2009; Levineaug, 2012; Iliea and Tirdia, 2015; Kavita, 2019 and Nunez, Regueiro, Suarez, Pinero, Rodicio and Valle, 2019 showed that there is a connection between parenting style or parental involvement with understudy intrinsic motivation. Investigation of Gota, 2012 investigated parenting styles had a critical and positive direct impact on academic achievement motivation for female understudies.

Objectives

1. To find out the relationship between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).
2. To find out the relationship between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).
3. To find out the relationship between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).

Hypotheses

1. There exists significant relationship between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).
2. There exists significant relationship between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).

Optimal Motivation among Adolescents in Relation to Parental Involvement

3. There exists significant relationship between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).

II. RESEARCH DESIGN

In present examination, a quantitative, descriptive and relationship overview strategy was utilized. The principle objective of the current exploration was to investigate the relationship between optimal motivation of adolescents and dimensions of parental involvement. The method utilized in the current examination is quantitative as this methodology of studies is utilized to evaluate the problem with the guide of creating statistical records that might be changed over into useable realities.

Target Population

In the current examination populace comprised the understudies of ninth and tenth concentrating in C.B.S.E. affiliated schools of Ludhiana region of Punjab has been taken. Nonetheless, because of colossal size of populace, researcher routinely can't test each man or woman in the populace since its miles also steeply-valued and tedious. That is the reason investigator is predicated on examining systems.

Procedure

A past arrangement was fixed with school specialists after settled on previously mentioned (schools of Ludhiana area) to notify them about the objectives of the current research and to accomplish their authorization for measurements series. A speculative time table for realities series changed into then coordinated in conversation with the specialists. Records were procured subsequent to sharing the objectives of the present study and ensuring the members roughly their namelessness and the classification of realities they could be giving. Data became amassed with the help of Optimal Motivation Scale developed by the investigator and Parental Involvement Scale by Tramma, 1998. The instruments used to secure realities have been administrated in one meeting. To guarantee validity of the records, researcher mentioned the understudies to be straightforward in giving reactions. Enough time become given to permit the understudies to finish their tests at his/her comfort. After the test transformed into over, sheets were gathered, recorded and analyzed.

Sample and Sampling Method

Inside the current research simple random technique, stratified and systematic random sampling strategy and purposive sampling procedures had been embraced. At first, list of the schools affiliated to C.B.S.E. were downloaded from site (www.justdial.com). There were 188 schools around then. After that 10 schools were settled on by utilizing lottery procedure of simple random sampling method. By utilizing purposive inspecting method the analyst chose students based on educational qualification of the father and mother (graduate or under-graduate). After that a rundown was coordinated based on gender. To fulfil the purpose of the study sample of 464 adolescents have been drawn.

Tools Used for Data Collection

- Optimal Motivation Scale developed by the investigator.
- Parental Involvement Scale by Tramma (1998).

Statistical Techniques Employed

Karl Pearson coefficient of Correlation was employed to see the relationship between the variables under study.

III. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Table 1: Coefficient of Correlation between Optimal Motivation of Adolescents and Dimensions of Parental Involvement

Variables	Category	N	R	Sig./Not Sig.
Optimal Motivation and Personal Involvement	Adolescents	464	0.17	Sig. at .01
Optimal Motivation and Cognitive Stimulation	Adolescents	464	0.24	Sig. at .01
Optimal Motivation and Behaviour Involvement	Adolescents	464	-0.06	Non Sig.
Optimal Motivation and Cognitive Behaviour	Adolescents	464	0.06	Non Sig.

Optimal Motivation among Adolescents in Relation to Parental Involvement

Table 1 shows that

- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.17 which is significant at 0.01 level. Table further shows that there exists a positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.24 which is significant at 0.01 level which further shows that there exists a positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is -0.06 which is not significant at 0.01 level and 0.05 level which further shows that there exists negative relationship between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.06 which is not significant at 0.01 level and 0.05 level which shows that there exists positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

Therefore hypothesis 1 stating that “There exists significant relationship between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour),” stands partially accepted. The results of the study are in sync with studies of Gottfried, Fleming and Gottfried, 1994; Alyssa, Willems and Holbein, 2005; Gonida, 2007; Hoang, 2007; Grolnick, Friendly and Bellas, 2009; Levineaug, 2012 and Iliea and Tirdia, 2015 that shows significant relationship between parenting style or parental involvement with student intrinsic motivation.

The findings of the study further unveil that parents personal involvement and their cognitive stimulation to adolescents thoughts and feelings is positively correlated with optimal motivation of adolescents which indicates that more personal involvement and cognitive stimulation by parents leads to more optimal motivation among adolescents; as far as the behaviour involvement and cognitive behaviour of parents is concerned it is found that it is negatively correlated with optimal motivation of adolescents which shows that more behaviour involvement of parents and cognitive behaviour of parents tends to less optimal motivation among adolescents.

Table 2: Coefficient of Correlation between Optimal Motivation of Male Adolescents and Dimensions of Parental Involvement

Variables	Category	N	R	Sig./Not Sig.
Optimal Motivation and Personal Involvement	Male Adolescents	232	0.11	Not Sig.
Optimal Motivation and Cognitive Stimulation	Male Adolescents	232	0.21	Sig. at .01
Optimal Motivation and Behaviour Involvement	Male Adolescents	232	-0.04	Not Sig.
Optimal Motivation and Cognitive Behaviour	Male adolescents	232	0.05	Not Sig.

Table 2 shows that

- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.11 which is not significant at both level of confidence. Table further shows that there exists a positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.21 which is significant at 0.01 level which further shows that there exists a positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is -0.04 which is not significant at 0.01 level and 0.05 level which further shows that there exists negative relationship between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.05 which is not significant at 0.01 level and 0.05 level which shows that there exists positive relationship

Optimal Motivation among Adolescents in Relation to Parental Involvement

between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

Therefore hypothesis 2 stating that “There exists significant relationship between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour),” stands partially accepted.

The findings of the study reveal that parents personal involvement, their cognitive behaviour and cognitive stimulation is positively correlated with Optimal Motivation of male adolescents which means that more personal involvement, cognitive behaviour and cognitive stimulation by parents leads to more optimal motivation among male adolescents; as far as the behaviour involvement of parents is concerned it is negatively correlated with optimal motivation of adolescents that indicates where there is more behaviour involvement of parents there is less optimal motivation among male adolescents .

Table 3: Coefficient of Correlation between Optimal Motivation of Female Adolescents and Dimensions of Parental Involvement

Variables	Category	N	R	Sig./Not Sig.
Optimal Motivation and Personal Involvement	Female adolescents	232	0.25	Sig. at .01
Optimal Motivation and Cognitive Stimulation	Female adolescents	232	0.28	Sig. at .01
Optimal Motivation and Behaviour Involvement	Female adolescents	232	-0.17	Sig. at .01
Optimal Motivation and Cognitive Behaviour	Female adolescents	232	0.07	Not Sig.

Table 3 shows that

- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.25 which is significant at 0.01 level. Table further shows that there exists a positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.28 which is significant at 0.01 level which further shows that there exists a positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is -0.17 which is significant at 0.01 level which further shows that there exists negative relationship between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.07 which is not significant at 0.01 level and 0.05 level which shows that there exists positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

Therefore hypothesis 3 stating that “There exists significant relationship between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour),” stands partially accepted.

The findings of the study reveal that parents personal involvement and their cognitive stimulation is positively correlated with optimal motivation of female adolescents which means that where there is more personal involvement and cognitive stimulation there is more optimal motivation among female adolescents; as far as the behaviour involvement and cognitive behaviour of parents is concerned it is negatively correlated with optimal motivation of female adolescents which explores that cognitive behaviour and more behaviour involvement tends to less optimal motivation among female adolescents.

IV. FINDINGS

1. Findings of the correlational analysis between the variable Optimal Motivation of adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement

- (a) There exists a significant positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- (b) There exists a significant positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension

Optimal Motivation among Adolescents in Relation to Parental Involvement

of Parental Involvement.

(c) There exists non-significant negative relationship between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.

(d) There exists non-significant positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

2. Findings of the correlational analysis between the variable Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement

(a) There exists non-significant positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.

(b) There exists a significant positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement.

(c) There exists non-significant negative relationship between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.

(d) There exists non-significant positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of male adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

3. Findings of the correlational analysis between the variable Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement

(a) There exists a significant positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.

(b) There exists a significant positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement.

(c) There exists significant negative relationship between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.

(d) There exists non-significant positive relationship between Optimal Motivation of female adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

V. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The current research explores positive relationship between optimal motivation with personal involvement and cognitive stimulation dimension of parental involvement. The current Review will assist the parents with being more occupied with the scholastic existence of their children so that they can feel more persuaded and can take insightful choices about their schooling and vocation. The findings further unveils connection between optimal motivation of female adolescents and dimensions of parental involvement which shows female adolescents feel all the more optimally spurred when their folks shows more interests in paying attention to them and examine their issues.

The review will direct the parents to be more involved, empower and propel their female adolescents so they can take insightful choices, feel more certain and skillful. The review would have pragmatic ramifications for the instructors, instructive organizers and strategy creators to coordinate such kinds of projects that assist the parents with knowing the significance of optimal motivation and approaches to rouse the female adolescents and furthermore manual for outline arrangements and give offices which will help the female adolescents to be feel all the more optimally motivated.

The review will likewise help the parents, educators and instructive overseers to comprehend and regard the independence, decisions and choices of adolescents with the goal that they can feel optimally motivated. The review would urge the parents to examine and impart issues to their male and female adolescents. The review would have practical significance for understudies additionally really know how much parental inclusion, their direction and motivation is useful for them in making scholarly progress just as achievement in profession.

VI. CONCLUSION

Under the light of above examination the investigator arrive at the conclusion that parent's involvement assume critical part in giving independence and opportunity of decision to their children in training and career that helps them in dynamic and make them optimal motivated. Optimal motivation in the academics and professional lives ends up being an intense apparatus in upgrading scholarly execution, using sound judgment, knowing the significance of accomplishing any work with delight and euphoria to make progress in schooling just as throughout everyday life. The results of the investigation unveil the significance of abilities and capabilities in any field of life.

Optimal Motivation among Adolescents in Relation to Parental Involvement

REFERENCES

- 1) Alyssa, R.G.D., Willems, P.P. and Holbein, M.F.D. 2005. Examining the relationship between parental involvement and student motivation. *Educational Psychology Review*, 17(2), 99- 123. Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10648-005-3949-7> on 5/4/19
- 2) Bedi, J. 2020. Goal setting, optimal motivation and academic performance of adolescents in relation to parental involvement. Ph.D. thesis, Panjab University, Chandigarh.
- 3) Berthelsen, D. and Walker, S. 2008. Parents' involvement in their children's education. *Family Matters*, 79, 34-4.
- 4) Best, J. W. and Kahn, J. 1990. *Research in education*. New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.
- 5) Garrett, H. E. 1981. *Statistics in psychology and education*. McGraw Hill: Tokyo. p. 9. *Genetic Psychology Monographs*, 75(1), 43–88.
- 6) Gonida, E.N. 2007. Parental influences on student motivation, affect and academic behaviour: Introduction to the special issue. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 21(1), 3 6. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/...Parental...mottivation.../553df25c0cf29b5ee4bcea0a.pd...on 9/4/17>.
- 7) Gota, A.A. 2012. Effects of parenting styles, academic self-efficacy, and achievement motivation on the academic achievement of university students in Ethiopia. Retrieved from <http://ro.ecu.edu.au/theses/461> on 11/5/17.
- 8) Gottfried, A.E., Fleming, J.S. and Gottfried, A.W. 1994. Role of parental motivational practices in children's academic intrinsic motivation and achievement. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 86(1), 104-113.
- 9) Grolnick, W.S., Friendly, R.W. and Bellas, V.M. 2009. Parenting and children's motivation at school. In K. R. Wentzel & A. Wigfield (Eds.), *Handbook of motivation at school*, 279- 300. New York & London: Routledge.
- 10) Hoang, T.N. 2007. The relations between parenting and adolescent motivation. *International Journal of Whole Schooling*, 3(2). Retrieved from <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ847476.pdf> on 3/3/17.
- 11) Hoover, D., Kathleen, V. and Sandler, H.M. 1995. Parent involvement in children's education: Why does it make a difference? *Teachers College Record*, 97, 310–331.
- 12) Iliea, M. P. and Tirdia, F.A. 2015. Parental involvement and intrinsic motivation with primary school students . *Procedia – Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 187, 607-612. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042815019060> on 12/6/17
- 13) Kavita 2019. Self regulated learning among secondary school students in relation to their motivational beliefs and perceived parental involvement. Doctoral thesis, 20. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/288835> on 14/7/2020.
- 14) Levineaug, M. 2012. Raising successful children. *The New York Times*, retrieved from <http://www.nytimes.com/2012/08/05/opinion/sunday/raising-successful-children.html> on 10/6/17.
- 15) Nihat, Sad, S. and Gurbuzturk, O. 2013. Primary school students' parents' level of involvement into their children's education. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 13(2). Educational Consultancy and Research Center. Retrieved from www.edam.com.tr/estp on 21/7/19.
- 16) Nunez, J.C., Regueiro, B., Suarez, N., Pineiro, I., Rodicio, M.L. and Valle, A. 2019. Student perception of teacher and parent involvement in homework and student engagement: The mediating role of motivation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1384. Retrieved from <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01384/full> on 30/11/19.
- 17) Peters, M. 2012. Parental involvement: How much is enough and what can schools do to encourage it? Master thesis, William Paterson University of New Jersey.
- 18) Rea, W. D. 2000. Optimal motivation for talent development. *Journal for the Education of the Gifted*, 23(2) retrieved from <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.4219/jeg-2000-574> on 19/4/17.
- 19) Rivers, J. 2008. The relationship between parenting style and academic achievement and the mediating influences of motivation, goal-orientation and academic self-efficacy. Ph.D. thesis, Florida state university college of human sciences. Retrieved from <https://diginole.lib.fsu.edu/islandora/object/fsu:176346/datastream/PDF/view> on 18/7/19.
- 20) Trama, S. 1998. A study of academic achievement in relation to intelligence parental involvement and childrens motivational resources control understanding perceived competence and self regulation at upper elementary and secondary school levels. Ph.D. thesis, Panjab University, Chandigarh. Retrieved from <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/80506> on 28/11/16.
- 21) Webster-Stratton C. 1998. Preventing conduct problems in Head Start children: Strengthening parenting competencies. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 5, 715–730 .[.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00220973.1991.10806563](http://doi.org/10.1080/00220973.1991.10806563) on 12/11/16.